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God, Why was My Child born Autistic?

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Abstract

This short article asks a sensitive and deeply pastoral question that is frequently asked by many parents who have children born with special needs, and more so, if their children are diagnosed with autism: “Why was my child born autistic?” The author, an ordained missioner, who has been working with parents and their children with special needs, provides a biblical perspective that Christian parents may find helpful, and then connects it with the grief cycle (Kübler-Ross model: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, acceptance) to show how faith, scripture, and theology can guide them through each stage.

Keywords: *Autism, Bible, God, Grief Cycle, Why*

1. Defining Autism

The Swiss psychiatrist, Dr Eugen Bleuler, coined the term ‘autism’ to describe a symptom of schizophrenia, characterized by extreme self-isolation and detachment from reality (Bleuler, 1911; see also Moskowitz & Heim, 2011). With the publication of the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association/APA, 2013), autism has been termed as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), a single diagnostic category encompassing a wide range of symptoms and severities (APA, 2013; Shaw, 2024).

Today, autism is best understood as a complex neurodevelopmental disorder involving persistent challenges in social communication, restricted interests, and repetitive behaviors, with known constitutional (genetic) bases and wide individual variability (Chia, 2025a). The original term of autism has since evolved far beyond Bleuler’s concept of the condition (Evans, 2013).

Although autism is not explicitly mentioned in the Bible, both Testaments offer theological principles on dignity, difference, and inclusion that can inform a biblical understanding of autism. Disability theologians further emphasize that Scripture should affirm neurodivergent individuals as integral to God’s good creation (Chia, 2025b).

2. A Biblical Perspective on Autism and the Grief Process

From a biblical worldview, autism is not a “punishment” nor a mistake. Scripture reminds us that all children are created in God’s image and have inherent worth (Genesis 1:27, NIV; Psalm 139:13-14, NIV).

Disability, including autism, is part of the brokenness of creation (Romans 8:20-22, NIV). However, God works through it for His glory. When Jesus was asked about a man born blind, He replied: “Neither this man nor his parents sinned...but this happened so that the works of God might be displayed in him” (John 9:3, NIV).

Thus, a child with autism is not a sign of failure or divine judgment, but an opportunity for God’s love and grace to shine uniquely (Swinton, 2012).

3. The Grief Cycle & Christian Hope

Many parents of children born with special needs often struggle to come to terms with the reality that the child they envisioned has turned out very differently: almost like a changeling! Similarly, Christian parents of children with autism may face a similar struggle as they work through acceptance and navigate the various stages of grief (Kübler-Ross, E., & Kessler, 2014; also see Robinson, 2020; see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1. The Model of Grief Cycle

3.1. *Denial*: Parents may initially struggle to accept the diagnosis, hoping their child will outgrow it. God knows their fears (Isaiah 43:1, NIV). Acknowledging autism is not giving up faith. In fact, it is stepping into the reality where God can heal and guide (Robinson, 2020).

3.2. *Anger*: Some parents feel anger at God, doctors, or themselves, “Why us? Why my child?” The Bible acknowledges anger and lament (Job 3:1-26, NIV; Psalm 62:8, NIV). Anger can be an honest prayer to God; He can handle their questions.

3.3. *Bargaining*: Parents may plead with Go, “If I pray harder, if I do everything right, maybe my child will be healed.” God hears prayers but His will is sovereign (Luke 22:42, NIV). While complete ‘cure’ (I, personally, do not deny that miracle is still possible) may not come, God promises sustaining grace (2 Corinthians 12:9, NIV).

3.4. *Depression*: Feelings of sadness often set in when parents realize lifelong challenges ahead. The Holy Bible assures us that “[T]he Lord is close to the broken hearted” (Psalm 34:18) and often reminds us to “[C]ast all your anxiety on him because he cares for you” (1 Peter 5:7). Even Christ wept (John 11:35, NIV). Depression is not weak faith but human lament (Kübler-Ross & Kessler, 2014).

3.5. *Acceptance*: This acceptance does not mean resignation but embracing the child as God's beloved gift. Parents move from "Why?" to "How can I nurture my child fully?" (Jeremiah 29:11, NIV; Ephesians 2:10, NIV). It is important to note that autism is not an obstacle to God's image. However, it is just another way to express it (Yong, 2011).

4. Closing Word of Hope

Christian parents can be assured that their child is fearfully and wonderfully made (Psalm 139:14, NIV), deeply loved by God, and not defined by a diagnosis. Autism may change the parenting journey, but it does not diminish God's purposes. Each stage of grief is a pathway where God's presence, grace, and community can bring healing and hope.

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